

Effect of Electronic Word of Mouth (E-wom), Brand Ambassador, and Price on Purchasing Interests in Products of Industrial Cosmetics among University Students During Pandemic Covid-19

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Abstract- This study aims to examine and analyse the effect of electronic word of mouth (eWOM), brand ambassadors, and prices on purchasing an interest in Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia during the COVID-19 pandemic. The population of this research is University students who are interested in buying products from Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia. A purposive sampling method was done to derive 108 samples. The data analysis method used is multiple linear regression analysis. The results showed that electronic word of mouth (eWOM), brand ambassadors, and prices each significantly affected Purchase Interest in Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia for university students during the COVID-19 pandemic. The research implies that healthcare and beauty cosmetics products are persistent during the pandemic.

Keywords:- *Electronic Word of Mouth(Ewom), Brand Ambassador, Prices, Purchase Interest.*

I. INTRODUCTION

High mobility and increasingly dense activities make people pay less attention to the surrounding environment. Many are looking for something more practical and instant to meet their daily needs. Today, trade is increasingly free, and many companies create diverse products. With the increasing number of instant products that will hurt public health, there is a need for health support products to maintain personal appearances, like the need for health supplements and skincare to keep the body healthy and well-groomed.

A person's buying behavior can vary [1]. This is due to the different people's preferences and attitudes in evaluating a product. The existence of different market segments causes the needs and desires of each consumer of a different product. Every company must understand consumer behavior towards the products offered [2] [3] [4]. Many companies offer these supporting products in terms of health and beauty. Companies

that have been established for a long time or have just been established provide various products that the community can choose according to their needs and desires.

Some companies, such as industrial cosmetics in Indonesia, K-Link, Oriflame, Herbalife and others offer a variety of products to meet the needs of supplements and skincare needed by the community. Industrial cosmetics in Indonesia are now more widely seen because it has several advantages not shared by similar companies. Industrial Cosmetic in Indonesia is a goods supply company engaged in health and beauty. This company is a direct-selling company that already has 55 branch offices throughout Indonesia and is a company that is developing following the development of the 4.0 industry. Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia provides KK Mobile applications for resellers to access transactions online more easily. And at this time, Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia continues to grow, and its product users are increasing, considering that in 2025 Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia will become the only direct-selling company that goes public.

The marketing system of Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia is very compatible with the variables to be studied. The company is making the transition and promotion of promotion and marketing strategies through electronic media and the internet[5]–[8]. Social media is also very influential in the transition of the company's marketing strategy now. Previously, only direct selling now turned to strategies following the development of industry 4.0 or internet marketing to influence purchase intention.

The consumer purchase intention is the desire of a consumer towards the fulfilment of needs and desires that are hidden in the minds of consumers. Consumer purchase intention is always veiled in everyone, where no one can know what is desired and expected by consumers. Authors explain that interest is an impulse or a strong internal stimulus that motivates actions where stimuli and positive feelings about the

product influence these impulse factors that affect a person's purchase intention, such as electronic word of mouth (eWOM), brand ambassador and price.

Electronic word of mouth is a positive or negative statement made by potential customers or former customers about products aimed at many people or institutions via the internet. Research that supports Electronic word of mouth (eWOM) influences purchase intention [9]–[12]. In this era of globalization, the development of the sales system is very rapid. The development of the internet was very influential in the sale of products by every company. The rapid progress of the internet can provide information choices about a product. Not only is it a form of person-to-person communication about a product or a brand, but it can also be a form of WOM communication that propagates through social media, which we usually call electronic word of mouth (eWOM). Electronic word of mouth (eWOM) will affect the purchase interest.

In the marketing system of industrial cosmetics in Indonesia, consumers were always looking for references or information from a community or people around whom we often call word of mouth (WOM). The development of information and communication technology makes product sales by resellers of this company add to the way of selling and promoting. Resellers use social media like Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp and others as media to market their products. The number of recommendations through the comments on social media using brand ambassador causes the public to be interested in Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia to buy their products.

Brand ambassadors can also influence a person's purchase intention in addition to electronic word of mouth (eWOM). A brand ambassador is someone who specifically communicates a product [13]–[18]. The influence of brand ambassadors on purchasing interest is supported by research conducted by Utami et al., (2020), the results of the study indicate that the brand ambassador has a significant influence on purchase intention. Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia issued various promotion methods to influence the purchase intention of the community towards the company's products, one of which is using celebrities and influencers as Brand Ambassadors. Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia chose Puspa Dewi as the brand ambassador.

Purchase interest is also influenced by price [6], [19], [20]. Scholar study that the price factor has a significant influence on purchasing interest. Price is the factor that is considered the most attractive for consumers in influencing the purchase interest of a product. Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia has a variety of products offered at various prices, from tens of thousands to millions of rupiah.

This research was conducted to review the influence of electronic word of mouth (eWOM) variables, brand ambassadors, and prices on Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia towards purchasing interests. The purpose of this article is to examine and analyze the effect of electronic word of mouth (eWOM) variables, brand ambassadors, and prices on Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia towards purchasing interests.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Purchase intention

Attitudes toward Influencer fashion and toward the brand have a significant impact on consumers' purchase intention [21]. The customers in the AR application of the Ray-Ban eyewear brand toward brand trust and purchase intentions had a higher mean than both real experiences and traditional advertisement applications. Mobile applications purchase intentions are strongly predicted by attitude towards purchasing them [22]. This result upholds the TRA as well as theory planned behavior which consider attitude as the best determinant of intention. ([21]).

Consumers' attitudes and energy awareness. Consumers' attitudes are very crucial for buying intentions, and attitudes are a function of perceived benefits, perceived price and energy awareness Akroush *et al.*, [23] product affective involvement has a significant positive effect on purchase intention, but this effect is not significant in the relationship between product cognitive involvement and purchase intention. The critical factors including friend recommendation, opinion leader recommendation, quality of food safety Diffusion of food safety information through social media information, credibility of food safety information, demand for food safety information and perceived risk that affect the purchase intentions of customer through the diffusion of food safety information using social media. Social mindfulness (SM) was significant in explicating perceived convenience value, and convenience value significantly affects satisfaction and repurchase intention for smart wristbands [24].

B. Electronic Word of Mouth (E-Wom)

Besides WOM, electronic WOM impacts content marketing significantly. This study shows that electronic communication channels like Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube [12] Trust and e-WOM reviews are focal research topics. The increase in use of social platforms has facilitated the sharing of experiences and opinions between consumers. [25]. The consequences of social WOM marketing include some organizational and customer-related consequences. Among the consequences for the organization, 'improved customer-organization interactions' makes one of the most important consequences while 'products' promotion' is placed as the least important one by the experts [26].

e-WOM has a positive and significant impact on brand awareness [27]. The community-based video game market values user recommendations and reviews highly, as it is considered more trustworthy than professional critics The findings of this study suggest that high- versus low-involvement consumers will go through more EWOM information and spend more time with EWOM to develop an expectation or idea of the brand. Innovation relationship marketing in association with eWOM will satisfy brand resonance and its novelty needs. The valued relationship-marketing activities and effective eWOM will help organizations to face the competition successfully and build strong brand relationships [9]. The importance of word-of-mouth credibility on WOM adoption, the critical role tie strength plays, in this context, and the preference for the

readers' credibility assessment to be free from commercial influence[28]. The proposed hypothesis 1 is as follows:

• H1 : There is a significant influence of e-Wom on influencing Purchase intention Use either SI (MKS) or CGS as primary units. (SI units are encouraged.) English units may be used as secondary units (in parentheses). An exception would be the use of English units as identifiers in trade, such as "3.5-inch disk drive."

C. Brand Ambassador

Brand communities and influencer marketing are increasingly being seen as important ways for front-line employees to engage with customers in the service economy [13] [15] [18]. Another communication gap discovered in the language of brand ambassadors and prospective customers is differences in the use of past, present and future tense verbs reflecting a focus on different aspects of the purchase decision or customer experience.

Positive effect of celebrity brand ambassador on purchase intention. A famous celebrity that is well-known to have good personalities and is excellent at interacting with people/consumers will increase consumers' purchase intention. The result is equivalent with previous literatures that celebrity brand ambassador positively affects consumers' purchase intention Utami et al., [14] professional climbers, as brand ambassadors, engage in highly creative activities articulated around the need to produce and diffuse experiences of different kinds to create and foster work opportunities [15].

Ambassadors are motivated by product benefits and intrinsic reasons, and their experiences are impacted by factors relating to their personal expectations for the ambassadorship, whether they feel valued, and whether the benefits of the ambassadorship were worth the required work.[17] Branding has become an important aspect of many public sector organizations' internal and external activities [16]. The findings uncovered valuable information relating to brand ambassadors' experiences, including their motivations, benefits, and challenges of serving in this role brand ambassadors and the use of Instagram have a positive and significant effect on brand trust for Scarlett Whitening products

The proposed hypothesis 2 is as follows:

H2 : There is a significant influence of brand ambassador on influencing Purchase intention

D. Price

Prices have a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction in line with research by Albari & Kartikasari, [29]. Price had a significant effect on repurchase intention the relationship established by the regression coefficient is positive. The adoption of skimming pricing and penetration pricing is triggered by company-related factors that are associated with the company's corporate and marketing strategy and the product characteristics, while the adoption of pricing similar to competitive prices is influenced by market-related factors that are associated with customers' and competitors' characteristics [30].

Two main conclusions follow from the empirical investigation of the effects on sales of price and in-store temporary displays of promoted products across two different regions and channel formats of an emerging market . Guissoni et al., [19] the pricing process needed further study from a different perspective. The usual non-separation of companies into price-makers and price-takers and excessive focus on pricing approach rather than on pricing essence shows that changes in the way in which pricing is addressed were a must. Amaral & Guerreiro, [31] mentioned that the star rating is considered as a price-influencing factor to analyse differences in price sensitivity and the effect of bundling strategies between three- and five-star hotels [32]. The price, as a marketing-mix element, is particularly sensitive in franchise chains, because anti-trust laws prevent franchisors from imposing resale prices on their franchisees [33]. The proposed hypothesis 3 is as follows:

H3 : There is a significant influence of price on influencing purchase intention

III. METHOD

A. Type of Research

This research can be classified as explanatory research. Explanatory Research aims to examine the relationship between several variables by testing several hypotheses which are also testing the influence of the variables studied [34]. This research is in the form of qualitative data obtained from the results of a questionnaire, then the data is quantified using a Likert scale from 1 (very dislike) to 5 (very like). Primary data were obtained from respondents through questionnaires in the form of answers to questionnaires about Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM), Brand Ambassadors, prices and interest in purchasing Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia. The population in this study are all people who are interested in buying Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia. The sampling technique in this study uses the category of nonprobability sampling, which is done by purposive sampling method, namely sampling with minimum age criteria of 17 years, people who will or have already bought Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia and know the brand ambassador of Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia and has information about the products offered by Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia.

B. Population and sampling procedure

Population according to Malhotra & Birks, (2007) is the group of elements that possesses and sought of information to make an inference of the object. The population in this study are university's students in Jember region East Java who are interested in buying industrial Cosmetics.

The sample according to [35] is part of the number or characteristics possessed by the population. The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling, with certain considerations such as ; a. Respondents aged over 17 years old; b. will or have bought any brand of industrial cosmetics; c. well-know of industrial cosmetics ambassador in Indonesia.

In this study we use 108 samples where sample as a source of primary data. The data collected from respondents is the measured using Likert Scale from 1 (very dislike) to 5 (very like).

C. Research Framework

The research framework can be seen in Figure 1. below

The data is then analyze using multiple linear regression with the independent variable variables consisting of Electronic Word Of Mouth (eWOM) (x1), Brand Ambassador (X2), and Price (X3) on Purchase Intention (Y) as dependent variable as shown in the following equation:

$$Y = a + b1X1 + b2X2 + b3X3 + e$$

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of multiple linear regression analysis are shown in Table 1. Based on Table 1 the following equation model is formed:

$$\text{Purchase Intention} = 2,082 + 0,202 \text{ e-Wom} + 0,350 \text{ Brand Ambassador} + 0,266 \text{ Price} + e$$

Table 1. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Variabel	Regression Coefficient	Std. Error	Sig
Constant	2,082	,080	-
eWOM (X1)	0,202	,081	0,015
Brand Ambassador (X2)	0,350	,085	0,000
Prices(X3)	0,266	,085	0,002

Note : the DV is purchase intention

➤ **Multicollinearity Results**

The results of the multicollinearity test in this study are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Multicollinearity test

Variable	Collinearity Statistics		Information
	Tolerance	VIF	
e-Wom	0,985	1,015	No Multicollinearity Occurs
Brand Ambassador	0,913	1,095	No Multicollinearity Occurs
Price	0,904	1,106	No Multicollinearity Occurs

The results of multicollinearity testing where each variable has a VIF value <10 and tolerance value > 0.1 so that it can be concluded that overall, the variables eWOM (X1), Brand Ambassador (X2), and Price (X3), multicollinearity did not occur.

➤ **Heteroscedasticity results**

The results of the heteroscedasticity test in this study are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Heteroskedastisity test

Variabel	t	Sig
eWOM (X1)	-0,133	0,895
Brand Ambassador (X2)	0,959	0,340
Price (X3)	-1,515	0,133

Source: the results of the data are processed

Heteroscedasticity test results where each variable has a significance value of each variable has value > 0.05, so it can be concluded that overall, the variables namely Electronic Word Of Mouth (X1), Brand Ambassador (X2), and Price (X3) are not heteroscedasticity occurs.

Hypothesis Test Results (t-Test results in this study are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. t-Test Result

Variable	t Table	t count	Sig.	Test Result
e-Wom	1,658	2,475	0,015	H1 accepted
Brand Ambassador	1,658	4,140	0,000	H2 accepted
Price	1,658	3,124	0,002	H3 accepted

Source: the results of the data are processed

Table 4. explained that:

1. the electronic word of mouth t count of 2,475 is greater than t table 1.658 and the significance value of 0.015 is smaller than the significance of the 0.05 determination, means that accept H1. That is, electronic word of mouth partially influences the purchase intention of industrial cosmetics products in university's student
2. brand ambassadors of 4,140 is greater than t table 1.658 and the significance p-value of 0,000 ≤ α= 0.05 and accept H2. It means that the brand ambassador partially influences the purchase intention of industrial cosmetic products in university's student.
3. the price of 3.124 has a value greater than t table 1.658 and a significance p-value of 0.002 ≤ α= 0.05 and accept H3.

That is, the price partially influences the purchase intention of industrial cosmetic products in university's student.

➤ *The Effect of Electronic Word of Mouth on purchase intention*

The advent of the internet has allowed consumers to interact with each other quickly and easily and has also established a phenomenon known as interpersonal influence online or electronic word of mouth [36]. Electronic word of mouth is a positive or negative statement made by potential customers, actual customers and former customers about products or companies via the internet [37]. According to Goyette et. al. [38] information that can be obtained from electronic word of mouth is the number of opinions written by consumers on a social networking site, containing positive and negative opinions of consumers about products from social networking users, and the content of information from social networking sites relating to a product. Information obtained from electronic word of mouth will determine whether consumers have an interest in making a purchase or not.

Based on the results of the study the influence of electronic word of mouth variables on purchase intention obtained a significance value of 0.015. This value is smaller than the predetermined significant level that is equal to 5% or 0.05 and the coefficient value of the electronic word of mouth variable is 0.202 so the electronic word of mouth variable has a significant effect on Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia. This research is in accordance with research conducted by [10] [11] [25] who explained that electronic word of mouth had a significant effect on purchase intention. It can be concluded that the more positive electronic word of mouth that is created from the company to consumers will lead to consumer interest in buying Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia products.

➤ *Effect of Brand Ambassador on purchase Interests*

According to Hsu, (2022); Laric & Lynagh, (2009); Masterman & Wood, (2017); Paul, (2004) marketing communication is a means for companies to inform, persuade, and remind consumers directly about the products and brands they sell. According to a brand ambassador is someone who specifically communicates a product. The use of brand ambassadors can increase brand trust and attractiveness to buyers. Brand Ambassadors are expected to represent the wants and needs of prospective customers and be able to provide a positive image of a product and company.

Based on the results of the study the influence of brand ambassador variables on purchase intention obtained a significance value of 0,000. This value is smaller than the predetermined significant level of 5% or 0.05 and the coefficient value of the brand ambassador variable is worth 0.350 so the brand ambassador variable has a significant effect on Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia. This research is in accordance with research conducted by [13], [14] which explains that brand ambassadors have a significant effect on purchase intention. So it was concluded that the higher the brand ambassador has given by Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia to consumers will bring up consumer interest in buying the product.

➤ *Price Impact on Purchase intention*

According to Kotler & Armstrong, (2018) price is the amount of money charged for a product/service, or the amount of value exchanged by consumers for the benefits of owning or using the product or service. Price also means the amount of money that consumers must pay to get a product.

Based on the results of the study the influence of price variables on purchase intention obtained a significance value of 0.002. This value is smaller than the predetermined significant level is equal to 5% or 0.05 and the coefficient value of the price variable is equal to 0.266 so the price variable has a significant effect on the purchase intention of Industrial Cosmetic Indonesia. This study is in accordance with research conducted by [6], [20], [43]–[45] which explained that prices significantly influence purchase intention. It can be concluded that the better the price of the product given by industrial cosmetics in Indonesia to consumers raises the interest of consumers to buy the product.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on data analysis and scavenging about the influence of electronic word of mouth, brand ambassadors, and prices of industrial cosmetics among university's student during covid -19 era. The e-Brand ambassador becomes the first priority on influencing purchase intention of university's student in Jember region, East Java, Indonesia on consuming cosmetic or beauty products during pandemic Covid-19. The second criteria is then the e-Wom where the information about the products informed by the ambassador becomes consideration. This means that university student might consume the products as far as the artist is truly inform the positive things of the products. Once the ambassador (artist) is lie then he/she becomes the negative e-Wom among university's students. The last is the price of the product that influences the purchase intention. This research has been carried out in accordance with scientific procedures, but there are still limitations. In this study only measuring electronic word of mouth variables, brand ambassadors, and prices for purchase intention only, so this research still does not know how its determine the consumer's decision to actually buy products of industrial cosmetics among university's student in Indonesia.

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